

Special Needs Education

Country Data 2010

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2010

European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education

Education and Culture DG

Lifelong Learning Programme

The production of this document has been supported by
the DG Education and Culture of the European
Commission: [http://ec.europa.eu/
dgs/education_culture/index_en.htm](http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/education_culture/index_en.htm)

This document has been produced and published by the European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education.

Extracts from the document are permitted provided a clear reference to the source is given, as follows: European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education, 2010. *Special Needs Education Country Data 2010*, Odense, Denmark: European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education.

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More information regarding the systems of special needs education in Agency member countries is available from the National Overviews section of the Agency website: <http://www.european-agency.org/country-information>

ISBN: 978-87-7110-031-0 (Electronic)

ISBN: 978-87-7110-030-3 (Printed)

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Revised December 2011

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PREAMBLE

The Agency SNE data collection is a biennial exercise with data provided by the Representatives of the Agency. In all cases this data is from official ministerial sources. All data refers to pupils officially identified as having special educational needs (SEN) as defined in the country in question and all the data presented in this document has been collected in line with each country's own legal definition of SEN. These definitions are also provided in the texts.

Data provided by countries covers eight agreed questions – five are statistical:

1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN).
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings).
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools.
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools.
5. Pupils with SEN in inclusive settings.

Segregation refers to education where the pupil with special needs follows education in separate special classes or special schools for the largest part – 80% or more – of the school day. This operational definition has been agreed upon by Agency member countries.

The information submitted is raw data i.e. actual numbers of pupils registered in different settings.

The three remaining questions provide contextual information with notes and clarifications, particularly referring to legal definitions of special needs:

6. Compulsory age range with a specification of primary and secondary age phases if appropriate.
7. Clarification of public and private sector education.
8. The legal definition of SEN in the country.

Data was collected in late 2009, but sources used are from the academic years 2007/2008, 2008/2009 and 2009/2010.

The following notations are used throughout the document:

- * Indicates an associated note.
- 0** Indicates zero and not missing data.
- Indicates no data available.

AUSTRIA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Austria. Detailed statistical information for Austria is available from: http://www.statistik.at/web_de/statistiken/bildung_und_kultur/index.html The data presents the number of students from grade one to nine, irrespective of age.
	737,662		64,857				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	312,888	424,774	18,677	46,180	802,519	2008/2009	
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Austria.
	27,555		970				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	9,601	17,954	307	663	28,525	2008/2009	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Austria.
	11,276		511				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	3,205	8,071	161	350	11,787	2008/2009	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Austria.
	864		101				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	323	541	27	74	965	2008/2009	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Austria.
	15,415		358				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	6,073	9,342	119	239	15,773	2008/2009	
6. Compulsory age phase	9 years of compulsory education (age 6 to 15). 4 years primary education (age 6 to 10), 5 years secondary education (age 10 to 15).						

<p>7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education</p>	<p>Public schools are either financed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - completely by the federal state (teacher salaries, maintenance of school buildings) in terms of academic secondary schools, higher vocational schools, teacher training colleges etc.; - or financed by the federal state (teacher salaries) and the communities (school maintenance) in terms of compulsory schools (primary, lower secondary, special or prevocational schools); - or by the federal state (teacher salaries) and a federal province (school maintenance) e.g. vocational schools. <p>Private schools – The majority of private schools are (officially recognised) denominational schools and they are maintained by the respective church. The federal state is obliged to finance teacher salaries.</p> <p>Private associations who are in favour of a special pedagogy ('alternative pedagogy' like 'Waldorf' etc.) and who develop a particular curriculum that is not in line with the national curriculum are totally financed by their stakeholders. In case they fulfil certain given criteria they might also get financial support by the state authorities.</p> <p>If private schools follow the national curriculum they may be given the mandate by the Ministry of Education to provide legal state certification (private schools with 'public law status').</p>
<p>8. Legal Definition of SEN</p>	<p>A child is recognised as having special educational needs if – as a result of a physical or psychologically based disability – he/she is not able to achieve the goals of the national curriculum without receiving special provision (§ 8, Compulsory Schooling Act Schulpflichtgesetz).</p> <p>The assessment procedure is carried out by the school district board upon the application of the parents, the head teacher of the school or by the board itself with reference to expert opinions.</p> <p>SEN provision is available for two 'categories' of students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Category 1: pupils officially labelled as having special educational needs (pupils with physical and/or psychological disabilities) may either attend a special or a mainstream school with additional support (based on parental choice). - Category 2: pupils with special educational needs, but without certification (such as speech impediments, behaviour problems, visual or hearing impairments) are offered 'outpatient' provision by the Special Mobile Service in or outside classrooms. <p>The education of pupils with special educational needs is embedded in the general legislative framework for education such as:</p> <p>The 1962 School Organisation Act (Schulorganisationsgesetz) is the foundation on which the current school organisation (including education of Students with SEN in special schools (Sonderschulen) or mainstream settings) is based. The 'School Education Act' (Schulunterrichtsgesetz) is the legal framework for all issues concerning education within schools (e.g. assessment, enrolment of students, transition procedures within different types of schools etc.).</p> <p>Special Needs Education in Austria: important milestones are the 15th Amendment to the 'School Organisation Act' of 1993, the 17th Amendment of 1996 and the associated amendments of the 'Compulsory Schooling Act' (Schulpflichtgesetz), the School Education Act and of the 'Basic Act on the Maintenance of Compulsory Schools' (Pflichtschulerhaltungs-Grundsatzgesetz). These amendments have re-oriented the educational system by providing new organisational and integrative forms of special pedagogical assistance for pupils with special educational needs in general compulsory schools (Allgemein bildende Pflichtschulen).</p>

BELGIUM (FLEMISH SPEAKING COMMUNITY)

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	268,088		603,832 *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	871,920	2008/2009
	150,495	113,375 In addition: Part-time secondary: 3,352 Home educated: 866 **	258,930	341,319 Part-time secondary: 3,583		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	54,336		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	54,336 *	2008/2009
	32,068	22,268	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	17,430		28,661			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	46,091	2008/2009
	10,740	6,690	16,803	11,858		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	- *	-
	-	-	-	-		

Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education.

* These figures refer to Government dependant private schools only. Data for independent schools is not available. The number of independent private schools is very limited in the Flemish Community. This data is not collected by the Education Department.

** Home education means that parents educate their children themselves, at home. Parents have to prove to the inspectorate that they can provide quality schooling.

All pupils enrolled are taken into account (i.e. pupils outside the compulsory school age are within the data).

Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education.

* It is not possible to tell which of these pupils are in private or public education.

The numbers given in this table are restricted to pupils in special schools and pupils integrated in mainstream schools.

Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education.

* In the Flemish school system there are no special classes in mainstream schools. Pupils with SEN in mainstream schools are fully included.

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education. These pupils are included in mainstream classes for more than 80% of their school day. * It is not possible to tell which of these pupils are in private or public education.
	8,245 *		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	4,525	3,720			8,245	2008/2009	
6. Compulsory age phase	The age range covered by compulsory education is from 6 to 18 years old. Primary school: 6 to 12 years (compulsory). Secondary school: 12 to 18 years (compulsory).						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public education refers to community education and subsidised publicly run schools. Private sector refers to subsidised privately run schools. These are general Catholic schools and the Government finances them. The number of independent private schools is limited in the Flemish Community. Data on this type of school is not collected by the Department for Education and Training.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Special education is defined as: 'education, based on a pedagogical project that provides adapted schooling, care and therapy for pupils whose personal development cannot be or can insufficiently be guaranteed, temporarily or permanently, in a mainstream school.' 8 types of special education are distinguished. The same categorisation is used for funding integrated education. Reference: Decree, 1997.						

BELGIUM (FRENCH SPEAKING COMMUNITY)

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils <i>(including those with SEN)</i>	687,137		- *		687,137	2008/2009	<p>Source: ETNIC.</p> <p>For primary mainstream school: 692 pupils included in the numbers are not in compulsory age range; for special primary school, there are 10 pupils that are younger than 6.</p> <p>For the secondary level the number covers all students registered in the secondary level including some out of compulsory school because they are older than 18: 59,990 for mainstream secondary and 3,896 in secondary special schools.</p> <p>Not included in all these numbers: 177,452 pupils in pre-schools.</p> <p>* No data is available for pupils in private education. This applies to questions 1 to 5 (see also question 6).</p>
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	320,674	366,463	-	-			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN <i>(in all educational settings)</i>	30,993		-		30,993	2008/2009	<p>Source: ETNIC.</p> <p>This data is for students of compulsory school age.</p>
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	15,581	15,412	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	30,773		-		30,773 *	2008/2009	<p>Source: ETNIC.</p> <p>* This number includes students in non-permanent integration: 30 in primary schooling and 7 in secondary schooling.</p>
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	15,475	15,298	-	-			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* This data is not available.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: ETNIC. 76 students in primary and 107 in secondary school are in permanent integration and are included in the numbers of mainstream schools. This number represents only pupils who are new to integration for the reference year. The pupils already integrated in previous years are not included in these figures – they are counted in mainstream numbers (see also question 3).
	220		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	106	114	-	-	220	2008/2009	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The compulsory age phase is age 6 to 18.</p> <p>Primary school is from 6 to 12 and secondary school is from 12 to 18. In special schools pupils must stay in the pre-school until the age of 8 and in primary schools until the age of 15 with a special agreement reached by the council of the classes (the educative team of school, PMS centre and parents).</p>						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>The private sector receives no funding from the Community. They are obliged to follow the official programme that leads to the baccalaureate. Private schools make up a very small part of the education system; numbers are unknown.</p>						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>The Decree of the 3 March 2004 organising special needs education gives the following definition in article 2:</p> <p>§1 Specialised education is reserved for children and adolescents who on basis of a multidisciplinary assessment conducted by defined institutions on the basis of article 12, may access adapted education in relation to their special needs and pedagogical possibilities.</p> <p>These children and adolescents are identified as 'children and adolescents with special needs'.</p> <p>Specialised education is organised into 8 types. Each type is an adapted education associated with the general and particular needs of a group of children, whose needs belong to a same type and have defined as a function of the principal disability common to this group. For children with multi disabilities, the type of specialised education is defined according to the priority educative needs to be fulfilled in accordance with to the age and the possibilities of the child.</p> <p>Type 1 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with light mental disabilities.</p> <p>Type 2 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with moderate or severe mental disabilities.</p> <p>Type 3 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with behaviour and severe personality problems.</p> <p>Type 4 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with physical problems.</p> <p>Type 5 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with illness or convalescing (classrooms in hospitals).</p> <p>Type 6 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with visual impairment.</p> <p>Type 7 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with auditory impairment.</p> <p>Type 8 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with specific impairment.</p>						

CYPRUS

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	87,586		10,352			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	97,938	2008/2009
	61,225	26,361	4,868	5,484		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,445		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	5,445	2008/2009
	3,105	2,340	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	293		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	293	2008/2009
	293	- *	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	583		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	583	2008/2009
	343	240	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	4,569		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	4,569	2008/2009
	2,469	2,100	-	-		
6. Compulsory age phase	The age range is from 4.8 to 15 years old.					
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public Sector: refers to the education provided by the State, free of charge. Private Sector: refers to the education which is provided by non governmental institutions. These institutions are run by individuals, after gaining license to work by the State.					

8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>A child with special needs, according to the Law for Education and Training of Children with Special Needs 113(I) 1999, means a child having a serious learning or special learning functioning or adjusting difficulty, caused by physical, mental or other gnostic or psychological deficiencies and having need of special education and training. A child has a learning, special learning, functioning or adjusting difficulty if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- he/she has seriously greater difficulties compared to the majority of the children of the same age, or- he/she has a disability which excludes or hinders him/her from using the educational means of the sort schools generally provide for children of the same age.
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CZECH REPUBLIC

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	819,667		16,705			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	836,372	2009/2010
	453,823	365,844	6,931	9,774		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	69,083		2,796			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	71,879	2009/2010
	33,453	35,630	1,423	1,373		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	28,231		1,861			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	30,092	2009/2010
	12,755	15,476	972	889		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	6,904		122			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	7,026	2009/2010
	2,760	4,144	32	90		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	33,948		813			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	34,761	2009/2010
	17,938	16,010	419	394		
6. Compulsory age phase	6–15 years. Primary 6–11, Secondary 12–15.					

	<p>9 years compulsory school attendance. Children are allowed to start compulsory education later, but all children have to start in the school year when they reach the age of 8.</p>
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Public sector – schools established by Ministries, municipalities and regions.</p> <p>Private sector – school established by private bodies, church and/or denomination. All schools are entitled to state contribution. Private schools are authorised to ask for tuition.</p> <p>Schools run by private bodies are funded by 60% of the particular funding formula designed for public schools. Under certain conditions such as a very good external evaluation conducted by the School Inspectorate, the funding of such a school may increase up to 100%.</p> <p>The funding of schools run by church/denomination is based on the same principles as public schools.</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>A child/pupil/student with SEN is according to the law a child/pupil/student who is or is likely to be unable to benefit from school education made generally available for children/pupils/students of the same age without the provision of additional support. The group of pupils with special needs referred to in Question 2 is defined by the School Act, which specifies the group of children/pupils/students with special needs as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">a) Children/pupils/students with impairment – physical, mental, sensory, speech and language impairment, specific learning and/or behavioural difficulties, autism and children with severe multiple needs.b) Children/pupils/students with health risk conditions.c) Socially disadvantaged children/pupils/students. <p>The statistics provided in this table do not cover children/pupils/students described under sections b) and c) as for these groups no separate educational placement exists. To provide data about the mainstream/separate placement, the figures in the table only cover pupils mentioned covered under section a). These pupils have the right to be mainstreamed and/or educated at schools/classes organised for them.</p> <p>References and sources for this information are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The School act No. 561/2004;- Regulation on education of children, pupils, students with special needs and of gifted and talented children, pupils and students, No 73/2005.

DENMARK

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	594,844 *		124,300 **			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	719,144	2008/2009
	410,143	184,701	61,274	63,026		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	32,638		1,095			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	33,733 *	2008/2009
	18,306	14,332	251	844		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	12,148		609			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	12,757	2008/2009
	6,151	5,997	- *	609		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	18,986		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	18,986	2008/2009
	11,019	7,967	-	-		

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Uni-C, Statistics Denmark. * Pupils receiving more than 10 weekly lessons of special-needs education within the class. NB: Apart from those pupils individually integrated in extensive special needs education programmes, it is estimated that 22,000–23,500 pupils in the Danish Folkeskole receive support in or outside the classroom. Reference: 'Uddannelse – udvalgte nøgletal' [Key data on education].
	1,504		486				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,136	368	251	235	1,990 *	2008/2009	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>Compulsory education commences on 1 of August in the calendar year of a pupil's 7th birthday and terminates on 31 July of the year, in which he or she has received mainstream instruction for 9 years, not including the pre-school class.</p> <p>Primary school age is approximately 6 to 12.</p> <p>Secondary school age is approximately 13 to 16.</p>						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>The 9 years of compulsory education do not necessarily have to be spent in a municipal Folkeskole. They may instead be spent in a private school. The State allocates grants to private schools – corresponding to approx. 80% of the total expenditure of the schools. The teaching of the private schools must be on a par with that of the Folkeskole. Around 12% of all Danish pupils attend a private school. This percentage does not include the so-called Efterskoler, continuation schools.</p>						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Definition of SEN: People with severe physical and/or intellectual special needs (handicaps).</p> <p>Additional information: The teaching of children, young people and adults is regulated by a number of acts, and, with one exception (the act on special education for adults), the general provisions on special education are contained within the ordinary acts applying to the school area in question.</p> <p>In section 3 of the Act on the Folkeskole, it is laid down that 'Special education and other special educational assistance shall be given to pupils whose development requires special consideration or support', and it is directly mentioned that these provisions may contain deviations from the subject-range of the school, the provisions on proficiency assessment and the weekly timetable. (Additional information from the Danish National Overview 2010: www.european-agency.org/country-information).</p> <p>Reference: Ministry of Education, Denmark.</p>						

ESTONIA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	108,481		4,257			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	112,738	2009/2010
	69,976	38,505	2,971	1,286		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	10,080		355			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	10,435 *	2009/2010
	5,590	4,490	208	147		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	3,252		113			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	3,365	2009/2010
	1,839	1,413	50	63		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,380		79			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,459	2009/2010
	444	936	58	21		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,448		163			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	5,611 *	2009/2010
	3,307	2,141	100	63		
6. Compulsory age phase	Children who turn 7 years of age by 1 October of the current year are obliged to attend school. The compulsory schooling obligation applies to children until they acquire basic education or turn 17 years of age.					

7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Public schools are state and municipality schools. A private education institution is an educational institution based on the ownership of a legal person in private law and which shall operate pursuant to law, the legislation issued on the basis of law and the articles of association if the founder is a legal person in private law, and to its statute. (Private Education Institution Act § 2 (1) passed on 3 June 1998)</p> <p>All schools (public and private schools) are supported from the State budget for the teachers' salary, in-service training and buying schoolbooks.</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Pupils with special educational needs are pupils whose outstanding talent, learning or behavioural difficulties, health problems, disabilities or long-term absence from studies creates the need to make changes or adaptations in the content of studies, the study processes or the learning environment (study aids, classrooms, language of communication, incl. alternative communications, specially trained teachers, support staff, etc.), or in the work plan prepared by the teacher for work with the relevant class.</p> <p>Reference: Basic School and Upper Secondary School Act § 46 (1) approved on 21 June 2010.</p>

FINLAND

Question	Data				Notes and sources used		
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Finland. WERA web reports: https://www.data.oph.fi/wera/wera
	533,897		12,741 *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	546,638	2008/2009	
	346,082	187,815	5,013	7,728			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Finland. In Finland learners with special needs are classified into two basic categories: 1. Those with an official decision (45,493). The data presented here refers to pupils with an official decision. 2. Those without an official decision. This second group includes learners with minor learning difficulties (dyslexia, maths, speech difficulties etc.). There are 126,288 (2007/08) pupils who receive part-time special needs education.
	45,252		241				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	45,493	2008/2009	
	26,270	18,982	100	141			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Finland.
	6,541		241				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	6,782	2008/2009	
	3,872	2,669	100	141			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Finland.
	14,574		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	14,574	2008/2009	
	9,206	5,368	-	-			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Finland. Primary: 8,446 pupils study whole time in mainstream classes and 4,746 pupils study part of the school day in mainstream classes. Secondary: 4,336 pupils study whole time in
	24,137		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	24,137	2008/2009	
	13,192	10,945	-	-			

							mainstream classes and 6,609 pupils study part of the school day in mainstream classes. There is no data on what proportion of the school day pupils are in this setting.
6. Compulsory age phase	7–16 years.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	In Finland private schools are financed by the government and their curriculum is based on National Core Curriculum. Almost all pupils are in public sector.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Basic education is governed by the Basic Education Act (628/1998), the Basic Education Decree (852/1998), the Government Decree on the objectives and time allocation in basic education (1435/2001) and the National Curriculum 2004 given by National Board of Education.</p> <p>Learners have special educational needs when their possibilities for growth, development or learning are decreased due to disability, sickness or decreased functioning. Learners with need of psychological or social support or at risk in these areas have the right to support for learning.</p> <p>Pupils with minor learning or adjustment difficulties have the right to receive part-time special needs education in conjunction with mainstream instruction.</p> <p>If a child cannot cope in mainstream education due to disability, illness, delayed development, emotional disorder or some other similar special need, he or she may be admitted to special needs education. Special education is provided primarily in conjunction with mainstream instruction or in a special class or at some other appropriate location.</p> <p>Source: Statistics Finland.</p>						

FRANCE

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	12,542,100		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	12,542,100	2008/2009
	6,643,600	5,898,500	-	-		
Source: Ministry of National Education. Direction de l'évaluation de la prospective et de la performance (DEPP). Repères et références statistiques sur les enseignements, la formation et la recherche. Vanves: DPP, 2009. ISBN 978-2-11-097805-9 * Separate data for private and public education is not collected for all educational settings. This applies to questions 1–5.						
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	356,803		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	356,803 *	2008/2009
	177,597	179,206	-	-		
Source: Ministry of National Education, DEPP. * This total includes children in all special educational settings and they may be outside the age range of compulsory schooling. It is not possible to get data just regarding the compulsory school age range.						
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	75,504		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	75,504	2008/2009
	63,115	12,389	-	-		
Source: Ministry of National Education, DEPP. Special schools are specialised educational institutions from the medical, social and health sectors (full time schooling).						
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	161,351		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	161,351 *	2008/2009
	40,231	121,120	-	-		
Source: Ministry of National Education, DEPP. * The data covers group based education in compulsory education: - CLIS (primary schools); - UPI (secondary schools); - SEGPA (adapted general and professional sections), and - EREA (regional adapted education institutions) from the school adaptation sector. These are integrated settings, but pupils spend more than 80% of their school week in separate classes or groups.						

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of National Education, DEPP. * This data covers individual integration in compulsory education.
	119,948 *		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	74,251	45,697	-	-	119,948	2008/2009	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory school age range is 6 to 16 years (6 to 11 and 11 to 16). The legal limits of compulsory schooling, from age 6 to 16, are now largely exceeded both in legal texts and in practice. The data refers to school pupils aged between 2 to 20 years.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	The settings created by the Ministry of National Education or by non-profit organisations are for the most part financed by public funds. Free education and care are provided in all these settings, either segregated or inclusive settings, if they are registered by the proper authorities.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>There is no established term in France which refers to the population of children who benefit from specific measures defined on the basis of special educational needs: the terms used (disabled children, non-adapted children, which cover different types of situations) are all very specific, linked to certain connotations and marked by a historical situation.</p> <p>According to the law n° 2005-102 of February 11, 2005 for equal rights and opportunities, participation and citizenship of disabled persons: 'according to the definition of the present law, a disability is constituted by any limit on activity or restriction on the participation in social life endured by a person in his or her environment due to a substantial, durable, or permanent alteration of one or several physical, sensory, mental, cognitive, or psychic functions, to a multiple disability or to a disabling health problem.'</p> <p>The CDA (Commission on Rights and Autonomy), referring to the list of deficiencies, disabilities and disadvantages (order of January 9, 1989) and to the guide table (decree n° 2008-110 of February 6, 2008) will take a decision on the degree of deficiency and on the educational, therapeutic, material, and human assistance that can be provided to the disabled person.</p> <p>As for children and adolescents recognised as ill, decisions concerning admission to and release from medical institutions are based on a medical decision.</p>						

GERMANY

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	7,676,651		559,570		8,236,221	2007/2008	Source: KMK – Kultusministerkonferenz – the information covers the 16 German Bundesländer: http://www.kmk.org/statistik/schule/statistische-veroeffentlichungen/schueler-klassen-lehrer-und-absolventen-der-schulen.html Federal Statistical Office (2007/2008), General School Statistics.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	3,119,272	Lower Secondary: 4,507,230 Not allocated by level: 50,149	116,886	Lower Secondary: 415,980 Not allocated by level: 26,704			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	-		-		479,741 *	2007/2008	Source: KMK – Kultusministerkonferenz. * A complete breakdown of separate data for public and private sector is not available. The breakdown by school level is: - Primary: 167,526 - Lower secondary: 235,080 - Not allocated by level: 77,135 In this data 1,666 students above compulsory school age are excluded.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	330,859		68,370		399,229	2007/2008	Source: KMK – Kultusministerkonferenz.
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	101,754	Lower Secondary: 178,752 Not allocated by level: 50,353	15,502	Lower Secondary: 26,368 Not allocated by level: 26,500			

4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* No data is available regarding the numbers of pupils in segregated classes in mainstream schools in any sector or age phase.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	- *	-	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: KMK – Kultusministerkonferenz. All Länder provide for a number of integrated students in their school system. The proportion of integration varies between the Länder. * Separate data for public and private sector is not available. The breakdown by school level is: - Primary: 50,270 - Lower secondary: 29,960 - Not allocated by level: 282
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	80,512 *	2007/2008	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The duration of full-time compulsory education (compulsory general education) is 9 years (10 years in five of the Länder) and the subsequent period of part-time compulsory education (obligation to attend part-time vocational school) is 3 years. Full-time compulsory education lasts until the age of 16 years, part-time compulsory education lasts until the age of 18 years.</p> <p>Primary age range: 6 to 9; theoretical duration: 4 years.</p> <p>Lower secondary age range: 10 to 15; theoretical duration: 5 years, (6 years in five of the Länder).</p>						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Germany has public and private sector education. Both institutions exist side by side and co-operate with each other. As a guarantee under the Basic Law it is possible to establish private schools. This is combined with a guarantee of the private school as an institution. The constitutional law rules out a state monopoly of education.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>The current definition of special educational needs means specific support for disabled pupils. The area of responsibility of special needs education in the Federal Republic of Germany with respect to all organisational aspects refers to the special needs within the context of disability exclusively.</p> <p>Pupils experiencing problems as a result of certain handicaps and/or in need of additional educational support because of problematic situations, as well as students with temporary learning difficulties (e.g. slow learners, reading and writing difficulties) are supported by a combination of measures of differentiation within the structure of the general system of support. Remedial or individual educational programmes based on the general structure offer and give support for problem situations during the learning process. The Federal Republic of Germany has a comprehensive framework of special measures targeted to additional advice and support for all kinds of situations that might occur in daily school life.</p> <p>NB: the legal definition has to be so wide because of the different situations and laws in the Länder.</p> <p>Source: KMK – Kultusministerkonferenz.</p>						

GREECE

Question	Data				Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,381,251		65,047			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,146,298	2009/2010
	702,830	678,421	50,899	14,148		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	29,954		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	29,954	2009/2010
	22,347	7,607	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	7,483		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	7,483	2009/2010
	3,642	3,841	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	22,471		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	22,471 *	2009/2010
	18,705	3,766	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	- *	-
	-	-	-	-		

Source: Ministry of Education, Lifelong Learning and Religious Affairs: www.ypepth.gr

Source: Ministry of Education, Lifelong Learning and Religious Affairs.
* Data on pupils with SEN in the private sector is not available. This applies to questions 2 to 5.

Source: Ministry of Education, Lifelong Learning and Religious Affairs.

Source: Ministry of Education, Lifelong Learning and Religious Affairs.
* This is a change from 2008 data. A stricter application of the operational definition of inclusion has been applied. These pupils are placed in so called 'inclusive classes' (formerly called special classes). In inclusive classes special teaching is provided by specially trained teachers, outside the main school programme. This teaching covers 80% of the everyday school programme.

* This is a change from 2008 data.
Accurate figures on pupils with SEN who are fully included in mainstream classes are not available.

6. Compulsory age phase	Education in Greece is compulsory for all children between 5 to 15 years, i.e. pre-primary (Nipiagwgeio – 1 year), primary (Dimotiko – 6 years) and lower secondary (Gymnasio – 3 years). However, school age may begin from the age of 2.5 (pre-school age) to Kindergartens (private/public), which are called Childrens' Stations or Frefonipiakoi Stathmoi. Some of them also include pre-primary units, which are licensed to operate as pre-primary schools for one year.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>All schools in Greece, including private, are under the responsibility of the Ministry of Education, use the same curricula and, after graduation, all pupils take together the entrance examination for Tertiary Education.</p> <p>Pre-primary Education – No. of schools: 456, Teachers and specialists: 667, Pupils: 11,815</p> <p>Primary Education – No. of schools: 200, Teachers and specialists: 2,860, Pupils: 39,084</p> <p>Secondary Education – No. of schools: 119</p> <p>Reference: Ministry of Education Lifelong Learning and Religious Affairs, 2009/2010: http://www.ypepth.gr/el_ec_categoryssm211.htm</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>The new Law 3699/2008 'Special Education and education of people with disability or special educational needs' (see * below) regulates all the issues concerning the degree of the learning difficulties that pupils may meet during the everyday education process either in the mainstream or in the special system education.</p> <p>According to the Law 3699/2008 'Special Education and education of people with disability or special educational needs', the following are referred to as special needs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulties in learning due to sensory, intellectual, cognitive, developmental, mental and neuro-psychiatric disorders which are localised after a scientific and pedagogical evaluation. These difficulties influence the process of learning and school adjustment. Pupils with special educational needs are considered those pupils who have disabilities in motion, vision, hearing, who suffer from chronic diseases, disorders in speech, attention deficit, and all pervasive developmental disorders. - Special needs are also considered behaviours due to complex factors, i.e. cognitive, emotional, mental and social disadvantages deriving from the family and social environment. - Special educational needs are also the educational needs of 'pupils who have one or more mental abilities developed to a degree that exceed a lot the expected abilities of their age range'. <p>NB: Difficulties in learning that derive from the social and economic background of the learner as well as low achievers are not considered as pupils with special needs.</p> <p>* ΝΟΜΟΣ 3699/2008 – ΦΕΚ 199/Α'/2.10.2008, Ειδική Αγωγή και Εκπαίδευση ατόμων με αναπηρία ή με ειδικές εκπαιδευτικές ανάγκες, http://www.disabled.gr/lib/?p=17947</p>

HUNGARY

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,133,647		141,718			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,275,365	2008/2009
	728,830	404,817	60,471	81,247		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	65,448		5,299			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	70,747 *	2008/2009
	50,114	15,334	2,836	2,463		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	32,004		1,010			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	33,014 *	2008/2009
	22,464	9,540	353	657		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	-	-
	-	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	33,444		4,289			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	37,733	2008/2009
	27,650	5,794	2,483	1,806		
6. Compulsory age phase	6–18 years. Primary: elementary schools (6–14 year olds – ISCED 1.2).					

	Secondary: academic and vocational secondary schools (14–18 year olds – ISCED 2.3).
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public sector: schools and kindergarten are maintained by local and county government. Private sector: schools and kindergarten are maintained by the church, foundation or private person.
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>In the academic year 2007/2008 the Act on Public Education was modified with respect to the definition of the target group and in the 14/1994 Ministerial decree on qualification obligations and pedagogical special services regulating the operation of the expert committees (see: 10.6.4.). The background to this public education-political decision to change the legislation was a continuous increase in the number of children, students with special educational needs, more specifically those needing special education due to psychological development disturbances and the significantly differing rate among different counties. Based on the evaluations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- There was a revision of the learners involved based on strict criteria.- The need for special education was terminated if the severe and long-lasting recognised disorder of functioning or behavioural development were not justified, and- If the severe and long-lasting disorder of functioning or behavioural development were recognised, but were not due to organic reasons, and the student participated in corrective teaching-education in a special class, faculty or school, but subsequent assessment indicated that the student in the following academic year can participate in general, that is, integrated education. This assessment serves to hinder unreasonable segregation.

ICELAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	42,845		666			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	43,511	2008/2009
	29,306	13,539	554	112		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	10,518		132			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	10,650 *	2008/2009
	7,388	3,130	114	18		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	143 *		0 **			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	143	2008/2009
	68	75	0	0		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	348 *		0			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	348	2008/2009
	245	103	0	0		

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		10,159	Academic Year of Reference 2008/2009	Source: Statistics Iceland.
	10,027		132				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	7,075	2,952	114	18			
6. Compulsory age phase	6–16 years.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public sector is paid by the government or the municipality, private by others.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Act on the affairs of people with disabilities, No. 59/1992 1 article para 2: ‘Those who are entitled to services according to this Act are the mentally or physically disabled who need special services and support for this reason. This refers to mental retardation, psychiatric illness, physical disability, blindness and / or deafness. ... disabilities can also be the consequence of chronic illness as well as of accidents.’</p> <p>No. 92, 12 June 2008 Art 34: <i>Pupils with special needs</i>: At upper-secondary school level, pupils with disabilities, cf. Article 2 of Act no. 59 from 1992 on Affairs of People with Disabilities, and pupils with emotional or social difficulties shall be provided with instruction and special study support. Specialised assistance and appropriate facilities shall be provided as considered necessary by the Ministry of Education, Science and Culture. Pupils with special needs shall study side by side with other pupils whenever possible.</p> <p>The Minister of Education, Science and Culture may, with agreement with an upper-secondary school, authorise operation of special study programmes for pupils with disabilities in upper-secondary schools.</p> <p>Pupils with reading difficulties shall, whenever possible, have access to specialised instructional material. The upper-secondary school defines in its school curriculum guide how it conducts screening and analysis for dyslexia, as well as its measures for follow-up and support for pupils analysed as dyslexic.</p> <p>Upper-secondary schools shall strive to provide special support to pupils that have specific study difficulties or illnesses.</p>						

IRELAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	649,166		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	649,166	2008/2009
	406,518	242,648	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	33,908		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	33,908	2008/2009
	20,556	13,352	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	4,976		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	4,976	2008/2009
	4,976	-	-	-		
<p>Source: Department of Education and Skills.</p> <p>* The total figure provided applies to public sector schools only as private schools are not obliged to return data to the Department of Education and Skills.</p>						
<p>Source: Department of Education and Skills.</p> <p>* No breakdown is available for the private sector. This applies to questions 2–5.</p> <p>The figures provided here are totals for questions 3, 4 and 5. Please refer to explanatory notes provided for these questions.</p> <p>The figure for primary schools does not include children with high incidence SEN who are resourced under the General Allocation Model. These children receive additional support in schools without requiring formal diagnosis. Reliable figures for the number of children receiving additional support without a formal diagnosis are not available.</p>						
<p>Source: Department of Education and Skills.</p> <p>This figure refers to pupils of compulsory school age (6–16 years) in special schools.</p> <p>Special schools in Ireland are designated primary schools, but some special schools also provide education to children of secondary school age. Of the 4,976 pupils aged 6–16 years in special schools, 2,283 of these pupils are of secondary school age (13–16 years).</p> <p>In addition to the pupils of compulsory school age, 1,099 pupils outside of compulsory school age were enrolled in special schools i.e. pupils who are under the age of 6 years, or aged 17 years or over.</p> <p>The figures provided here for special schools refer only to special schools for pupils with assessed special</p>						

							educational needs. In the returns for previous years, the figures for special schools included schools for children with special educational needs, as well as other schools which cater for children who are not included in mainstream school environments, such as hospital schools, schools for members of the Traveller community and schools for young offenders. The latter categories are not included in this year's data.
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Department of Education and Skills. * There is a total of 2,931 pupils in special classes in mainstream primary schools. 2,380 is an estimate of those pupils aged 6–16, i.e. those who are in compulsory education. The figures provided here refer to primary schools only. Figures for pupils in special classes in mainstream secondary schools are not available for 2008/2009.
	2,380		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	2,380	-	-	-	2,380 *	2008/2009	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* The figure of 13,200 for primary refers to children with low incidence SEN, on whose behalf the NCSE has allocated resource teacher hours. This figure may not include a minority of children in the age range 6–12 years on whose behalf resource teacher hours were allocated before the NCSE assumed the resource allocation function in 2005. ** The figure for Secondary includes children in receipt of resources through the NCSE for both low and high incidence SEN.
	26,522		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	13,200 *	13,352 **	-	-	26,552	2008/2009	
6. Compulsory age phase	Education in Ireland is compulsory from age 6 to 16 or until students have completed three years of second level education.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public schools (including some fee-paying schools) are grant-aided by the State. Private schools do not receive funding from the State.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	'Special educational needs' means, in relation to a person, a restriction in the capacity of the person to participate in and benefit from education on account of an enduring physical, sensory, mental health or learning disability, or any other condition which results in a person learning differently from a person without that condition' (Education for Persons with Special Educational Needs Act 2004).						

LATVIA

Question	Data				Notes and sources used		
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: All data for questions 1–5 is taken from the statistics report of the Ministry of Education and Science. The data is available on the website: www.izm.gov.lv * Data about the number of pupils in private sector is included in data provided for questions 1–5. No separate data is available. There is also no data about those students of compulsory school age who receive their education in part-time schools or so called 'evening schools'.
	185,032		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	114,236	70,796	-	-	185,032	2008/2009	
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical data of the Ministry of Education and Science.
	9,057		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	5,765	3,292	-	-	9,057	2008/2009	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical data of the Ministry of Education and Science.
	6,363		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	3,722	2,641	-	-	6,363	2008/2009	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical data of the Ministry of Education and Science.
	1,175		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	949	226	-	-	1,175	2008/2009	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical data of the Ministry of Education and Science.
	1,519		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,094	425	-	-	1,519	2008/2009	

6. Compulsory age phase	Basic education is compulsory (Education Law, Section 4) in Latvia and it is from the age of 7 till 16 (9 years: grades 1 to 9), but it is possible to continue to acquire basic education until reaching the age of 18. Grades 1 to 6 (ages 7 to 13) could be called primary education and grades 7 to 9 (ages 14 to 16) lower secondary education, but in legislation these levels are not officially recognised.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>According to Education Law (1999) Section 23: Procedures for the Foundation, Reorganisation and Dissolution of Educational Institutions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. State educational institutions shall be founded, reorganised and dissolved by the Cabinet pursuant to a proposal by the Minister for Education and Science or the Minister for another sector. 2. Local government educational institutions shall be founded, reorganised and dissolved by local governments, co-ordinating with the Ministry of Education and Science or the relevant sector ministry and the Ministry of Education and Science. 3. Private educational institutions shall be founded, reorganised and dissolved by legal persons and natural persons. The State and local governments may participate in the foundation of the private undertakings (companies). 4. A foreign legal person may fund, reorganise and dissolve an educational institution in accordance with this Law and other laws, as well as with international agreements.
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>The Education Law, Section 1, paragraph 24 states that special education consists of general and professional education adapted for persons with special needs and health problems, or with special needs or health problems.</p> <p>The Cabinet of Ministers Regulation No 579, October 21, 2003 lists a number of diagnoses of impairments and disabilities and suggested educational curricula according to which a person could acquire his/her education. These regulations cover a wide spectrum of impairments and disabilities as well as the provisions the educational institutions should provide for pupils with SEN.</p>

LITHUANIA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Centre of Information Technologies of Education. * For pupils who have severe and profound dysfunctions it is compulsory to be in the education system in Lithuania until the age 21 years. These pupils have been included in data for questions 1 to 5.
	435,809		4,695				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	121,526	314,283	1,000	3,695	440,504 *	2009/2010	
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Centre of Information Technologies of Education.
	51,761		120				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	27,665	24,096	62	58	51,881	2009/2010	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Centre of Information Technologies of Education.
	4,218		35				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,296	2,922	12	23	4,253	2009/2010	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Centre of Information Technologies of Education. * Complete data for pupils with SEN included in mainstream settings in private schools is not available.
	855		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	264	591	-	-	855	2009/2010	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Centre of Information Technologies of Education.
	46,688		85				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	26,105	20,583	50	35	46,773	2009/2010	
6. Compulsory age phase	The compulsory education in Lithuania is 6/7 to 18 years. For pupils with severe profound dysfunctions, it can be 6/7 to 21 years of age. Primary education is 6/7 to 10/11 years of age. General lower secondary education is 10/11 to 16/17 years of age.						

	General lower secondary education (Gymnasium grade) is 14/15 to 16/17 years of age. General lower secondary education (Youth school) is 11/12 to 18 years of age.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	The Law on Education of the Republic of Lithuania (2003) Article 19: A school is considered to be private if its founder is a legal or a physical body; if a Lithuanian legal or physical body together with foreign legal or physical body is the founder of the school; if a foreign legal or physical body is the founder. No ministry, municipality, county administration, Parliament or Government can be the founder of a private school.
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Special Educational Needs means the need for assistance and services arising from the fact that mainstream education and self-educational requirements do not correspond with the possibilities of pupils with special needs. Reference: The Law on Education of the Republic of Lithuania (2003).

LUXEMBOURG

Question	Data					Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education. Luxembourg: www.men.lu * This data includes private schools, international schools and 'Deutsch-Luxemburgisches Schengen-Lyzeum Perl'.
	58,348		5,989 *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	64,337	2008/2009	
	42,324 Pre-primary: 9,966 Primary: 32,358	16,024	3,825	2,164			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education, Luxembourg. * No data available.
	1,374		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,374	2008/2009	
	1,049	325	-	-			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education, Luxembourg. * There are no special private schools in Luxembourg.
	663		0 *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	663	2008/2009	
	387	276	0	0			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* Separate data is not available as these pupils are considered to be on the roll of special schools.
	- *		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	-	-	
	-	-	-	-			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education, Luxembourg. * No data available.
	711		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	711	2008/2009	
	662	49	-	-			

6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory education in Luxembourg covers 11 years: two years of pre-primary school (4 to 6 years), 6 years of primary school (6 to 12 years), and the first three years of secondary school (12 to 15 years). 1 year of non-compulsory school is offered to children aged 3 to 4 years.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	The Luxembourg State is in charge of organising and controlling the educational system. Public and private schools teach the same topics. In Luxembourg most primary and secondary schools are public schools. Public education is free of charge. Private schools are nearly all Catholic schools and are not free of charge. Private schools in these figures are grant-aided schools. Non grant-aided international schools are not listed in these statistics.
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Law of Special Education of 1973: 'The Government makes sure that every child because of his/her mental, sensory, emotional or motor particularities gets the instruction required by his state or situation in the structures of Special Education.' Law of 1993 states that the named children can be included in mainstream schools.

MALTA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	29,762		18,832			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	48,594	2009/2010
	14,628	15,134	8,920	9,912		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,938 *		707			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,645	2009/2010
	1,051	887	332	375		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	137 *		0			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	137	2009/2010
	137 **	-	0	0		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	13		0			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	13	2009/2010
	13	0	0	0		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,788		707			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,495	2009/2010
	901	887	332	375		
6. Compulsory age phase	For mainstream settings compulsory school age is from 5 to 16 years. In special schools there is a concession to keep students up to the age of 19 years.					

7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Public sector education is where students attend educational provision provided by the State. Public sector education is free.</p> <p>Private sector education (also called non-state education) includes Church Schools and Independent Schools.</p> <p>Parents of children attending Church Schools do not pay tuition fees. These are subsidised by the State as per agreement between the Government of Malta and the Church.</p> <p>On the other hand, parents who send their children to Independent Schools pay fees.</p> <p>There are no segregated special schools in the private education sector.</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>A minor shall be deemed to have special educational needs when that minor has special difficulties of physical, sensory, intellectual or psychological nature. Article 45 (2), Education Act, 2006, Chapter 327 of the Laws of Malta.</p>

NETHERLANDS

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,411,194		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,411,194	2009/2010
	1,439,447	971,747	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	103,821		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	103,821	2009/2010
	55,998	47,823	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	64,425		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	64,425	2009/2010
	32,831	31,594	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	- *	-
	-	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	39,396		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	39,396	2009/2010
	23,167	16,229	-	-		
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>Compulsory schooling is from 5 to 18 years. This is a change since previous data collection exercises – the compulsory schooling period has been extended.</p> <p>Primary schooling is from 4 to 12 years of age.</p> <p>Secondary schooling is from 12 to 18 years of age.</p>					

7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Private schools do not receive any funding from the Government. No data is available on pupils in private education.
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>The law on the Expertise Centres (WEC 2003) states that pupils are eligible for special education if they meet certain criteria. These are largely based on existing practice.</p> <p>Criteria for the visually impaired are a visual acuity: <0.3 or a visual field: < 30 and limited participation in education as a result of the visual impairment.</p> <p>For hearing impaired pupils a hearing loss > 80 dB (or for hard of hearing pupils 35–80 dB) and limited participation in education are required.</p> <p>The decision to provide extra funding for mentally disabled pupils will be based largely on IQ < 60, for physically impaired and chronically ill pupils medical data showing diagnosed disabilities / illness are needed.</p> <p>The criteria for behaviourally disturbed pupils require a diagnosis in terms of categories of the DSM-IV, problems at school, at home and in the community and a limited participation in education as a result of the behaviour problems.</p>

NORWAY

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	599,965		15,918			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	615,883	2009/2010
	414,271	185,694	9,781	6,137		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	47,246		1,556			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	48,802	2009/2010
	27,984	19,262	777	779		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools *	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,838		91			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,929 *	2009/2010
	805	1,033	35	56		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,055		266			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	5,321 *	2009/2010
	-	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	40,353		1,199			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	41,552 *	2009/2010
	-	-	-	-		
6. Compulsory age phase	Age 6–15 (10 years of schooling).					

7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Private schools are regarded primarily as a supplement to local authority schools. Most private schools are run by religious denominations or by organisations representing specific views of life or alternative educational approaches. Some offer essential instruction that the local authority schools are unable to provide. Authorised private schools receive financial support from the State.</p> <p>Legal definition: Section 2-12 (Education Act). Private primary and lower secondary schools. The Ministry must approve private primary and lower secondary schools. Approval shall be granted when a school fulfils the requirements laid down in the Act relating to Primary and Secondary Education, especially when it comes to curriculum, assessment and the organisation of the pupils' learning environment. Persons who run private primary and lower secondary schools without such approval are liable to fines. In the case of foreign and international primary and lower secondary schools in Norway, the Ministry may grant exemptions from the requirements.</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Right to special education: pupils who either do not or are unable to benefit satisfactorily from mainstream tuition have the right to special education. In assessing what kind of tuition shall be provided, particular emphasis shall be placed on the pupil's developmental prospects. The content of the courses offered shall be such that the pupil receives adequate benefit from the tuition as a whole in relation to other pupils and in relation to educational objectives that are realistic for the pupil. Pupils who receive special education shall have the same total number of teaching hours as other pupils. Expert assessment: Before the municipality or the county authority takes a decision concerning special education or a decision concerning special educational assistance, an expert assessment shall be made of the pupil's specific needs. This assessment shall determine whether the pupil needs special education, and what kind of tuition should be provided. The expert assessment shall consider and determine the following – the pupil's benefit from mainstream tuition, learning difficulties the pupil has and other special conditions of importance to tuition, realistic educational objectives for the pupil, whether it is possible to provide help for the pupil's difficulties within mainstream educational provision and what kind of tuition it is appropriate to provide. The Ministry may issue further regulations concerning expert assessment. If the decision of the municipality or county authority differs from the expert assessment, it shall be explained in the grounds for the decision why the municipality or county authority is of the opinion that the tuition received by the pupil fulfils the pupil's rights.</p>

POLAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	4,427,016		84,107			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	4,511,123	2009/2010
	2,710,690	1,716,326	46,706	37,401		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	127,954		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	127,954 *	2009/2010
	70,097	57,857	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	59,880		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	59,880	2009/2010
	29,251	30,629	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	- *	-
	-	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	68,074		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	68,074	2009/2010
	40,846	27,228	-	-		
6. Compulsory age phase	Primary – from 6 up to 13 (for students with SEN it can be 2 more years – this means up to 15). Secondary – from 13 up to 16 (for students with SEN it can be 2 more years – this means up to 18). For students with SEN the compulsory education must be finished no later than when they are 21 years old (approximately).					

7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>In line with the Education Act of 1991, schools can be public and non-public. A public school is an educational institution established by the central administration, local / district / regional authorities, and other legal body or by an individual person. It provides free education and implements core curricula and assessment procedures established by the relevant Minister of Education.</p> <p>A non-public school is an educational institution run by the legal bodies or individual persons on the basis of their incorporation into the register of non-public schools.</p> <p>Non-public schools are financed within the framework of a general subsidy from the State budget and additionally by fees received from parents and funds.</p> <p>Non-public schools in Poland have the right to issue school certificates that are recognised by all other schools and by universities. Most non-public schools have small numbers of pupils and small classes.</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Special Needs Education concerns children and youth with developmental disabilities who require special organization of work, working methods and special equipment. It can take place in general schools, or special schools.</p> <p>Special education covers the following groups of pupils with special educational needs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- pupils with slight mental disability,- pupils with moderate and severe mental disability,- pupils with severe mental disability,- deaf pupils,- pupils with hearing impairment,- blind pupils,- pupils with visual impairment,- physically disabled pupils,- chronically ill pupils,- pupils with psychiatric difficulties,- autistic pupils and pupils with multiple disabilities,- pupils with social and behavioural problems,- pupils with speaking and communication problems. <p>Special needs education is regulated by the Act on School Education of 7 September 1991, with further amendments and the resolution of Minister of National Education about special needs education.</p> <p>All students with SEN receive assistance from Psychological and Educational Services Centres free of charge and on a voluntary basis. Results of psychological, pedagogical and medical assessment serve as a basis for qualifying pupils for suitable forms of education (general schools, integration schools, special schools) although the final decision is up to the parents.</p>

PORTUGAL

Question	Data					Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: School Census. 2007/08, GEPE, Ministry of Education.
	1,126,059		204,991				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	627,068	498,991	135,800	69,191	1,331,050	2007/2008	
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: MISI – www.misi.min-edu.pt
	33,234		2,660				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	21,792	11,442	2,660	-	35,894	2009/2010	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: GGF – www.ggf.min-edu.pt * There are no public special schools.
	- *		2,660				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	2,660	-	2,660	2009/2010	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	DGIDC (Innovation and Curricular Development Department), Ministry of Education. * No data available.
	2,115		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,692	423	-	-	2,115	2009/2010	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	DGIDC (Innovation and Curricular Development Department), Ministry of Education. * No data available.
	31,119		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	20,100	11,019	-	-	31,119	2009/2010	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory education covers from 6 to 18 years of age. Primary phase age ranges from 6 to 12 years of age. Secondary phase age ranges from 13 to 18 years of age.						

7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Private special schools are funded by the State.
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Definition of special educational needs: children and young people receiving special education because they have difficulties in their learning process and their participation considering the interaction between inter-related factors and limitations in their functioning (Portuguese law n.º 3/2008, 7 January).

SLOVENIA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	162,902		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	162,902	2009/2010
	162,902	-	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	10,504		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	10,504	2009/2010
	10,504	-	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,829		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,829 *	2009/2010
	2,829	-	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	400		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	400	2009/2010
	400	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	7,275		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	7,275	2009/2010
	7,275	-	-	-		

6. Compulsory age phase	In Slovenia only primary school is compulsory. Pupils aged 6 enter the 9-year compulsory school.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Private schools are not a part of the public educational system. Their status makes them distinct from those schools which operate on the basis of concession agreements and their programmes do not differ from programmes of public schools. The expression 'private schools' also includes private schools which carry out their educational programmes according to the internationally valid pedagogical principles (Steiner, Decroly, Montessori, etc.).
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>In legalisation there are the following groups of disabled children (pupils):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Children with mental disabilities; - Blind and children with visual impairment; - Children with hearing impairments and deaf; - Children with speech and language problems; - Physically disabled children; - Children with long-term illness; - Children with learning difficulties and - Children with emotional and behaviour problems. <p>The Placement of Children with Special Needs Act (2000, 2007).</p>

SPAIN

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,961,624		1,475,634			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	4,437,258	2007/2008
	1,751,267	1,210,357	856,117	619,517		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	77,015		27,328			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	104,343	2007/2008
	47,289	29,726	14,221	13,107		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools *	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	9,686		7,714			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	17,400	2007/2008
	4,839	4,847	3,527	4,187		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	- *	-
	-	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	67,329		19,614			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	86,943	2007/2008
	42,450	24,879	10,694	8,920		

* The Statistical office does not provide this data. These pupils are considered pupils with SEN in segregated special schools so they are included in the data given for question 3 above.

There are pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools for two reasons: there is no segregated special school near the rural area; the segregated special school has not got vacancies and pupils have to be educated in a mainstream school.

6. Compulsory age phase	<p>6–15 years.</p> <p>Compulsory primary education: from 6 to 12 years.</p> <p>Compulsory secondary education: from 12 to 15 years.</p>
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Public education: the educational settings belong to the State. All the funding – including teachers' salary (teachers are civil servants) – is provided by the State, totally free of charge. The majority of Spanish pupils / students are schooled in this sector.</p> <p>Private education: private educational establishments are owned by private natural or legal persons. These private establishments may reach agreements with the Administration, in which case they are known as subsidised private schools. Parents pay for the schooling.</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Students with special educational needs refer to those who require certain support and specific educational attention due to disability or serious behavioural disorder, either for a period or throughout the whole of their schooling.</p> <p>It is the responsibility of the Education Administrations to guarantee and regulate the schooling of these children and ensure the participation of parents or guardians in the decisions which affect the schooling and educational procedures of these students. It is also their responsibility to adopt the appropriate measures to provide parents of these children with adequate individual assessment and the necessary information to help them in the education of their children.</p> <p>The schooling of students with special educational need will be governed by principles of normalisation and inclusion and will ensure non-discrimination and real equality in the access to the education system and continued attendance, allowing flexibility in the different stages of their education when necessary. The schooling of these students in special education centres or units, which may be extended until the age of twenty-one, will only take place when their needs cannot be met by the special needs provisions available in mainstream schools.</p> <p>The identification and assessment of the educational needs of these students will be carried out as early as possible by qualified professionals under the conditions determined by the Education Administrations.</p> <p>At the end of each school year the results obtained from each student will be assessed, according to the objectives set out in the initial assessment. This will allow the staff to provide appropriate guidance and adapt the learning programme in order to encourage, as far as possible, better integration of these students.</p> <p>It is the responsibility of the Education Administrations to provide infant school provision for children with special educational needs and to develop appropriate schooling programmes for them in primary and secondary schools.</p> <p>It is also the responsibility of the Education Administrations to encourage students with special educational needs to continue with the post-compulsory education as appropriate and to modify as necessary the testing procedures established in this Law for those students with disabilities.</p> <p>Pupils with special educational needs can attend both special education and mainstream establishments. Schooling should preferably be provided in mainstream establishments, adapting such programmes to each pupil's capacities.</p> <p>Reference: LOE: Título II, Capítulo I, Sección primera: Alumnado que presenta necesidades educativas especiales.</p>

SWEDEN

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	816,745		89,444			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	906,189 *	2008/2009
	-	-	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	13,220		557			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	13,777 *	2008/2009
	-	-	-	-		
<p>Source: Database of the Swedish National Agency for Education.</p> <p>* A breakdown of pupils in primary and secondary phases in both the public and private sectors is not available. This applies to questions 1 to 5. However, the breakdown of pupils across both sectors in primary and secondary education is as follows: Primary: 281 498; Secondary: 624,691.</p>						
<p>Source: Database of the Swedish National Agency for Education.</p> <p>It should be noted that there are no over-all statistics available for Sweden. In 2007 the Swedish National Agency for Education investigated the possibility of producing national statistics on pupils with disabilities. The National Agency found that such statistics would not be reliable, mainly because of the difficulty in defining what is to be counted as disability and how statistically to group the pupils and that it would shift focus from the responsibility of the school to support all pupils to the problems of the individual.</p> <p>* These pupils have cognitive disabilities who are enrolled in the special programmes and pupils who attend a national special school for pupils with visual impairment and additional disabilities or severe speech and language disorder or deafness or impaired hearing combined severe learning disabilities or congenital deaf-blindness. A breakdown of pupils in primary and secondary phases in each of the public and private sectors is as follows: Primary: 2,774; Secondary: 11,003. This figure includes 1,111 pupils above compulsory school age. These pupils are entitled</p>						

							to a voluntary tenth school year to broaden or deepen their knowledge.
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Swedish National Agency for Education. * These pupils attend a national special school for pupils with visual impairment and additional disabilities or severe speech and language disorder or deafness or impaired hearing combined severe learning disabilities or congenital deaf-blindness. This figure includes 85 pupils above compulsory school age. These pupils are entitled to a voluntary tenth school year to broaden or deepen their knowledge.
	516		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	101	415	0	0	516 *	2008/2009	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Swedish National Agency for Education. * These figures cover pupils with cognitive disabilities who are enrolled in the special programmes. These programmes are offered in every municipality and pupils are more or less included in the mainstream school. The breakdown of pupils across both sectors in primary and secondary education is as follows: Primary: 2,673; Secondary: 10,588. This figure includes 1,026 pupils above compulsory school age. These pupils are entitled to a voluntary tenth school year to broaden or deepen their knowledge.
	12,704		557				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	13,261 *	2008/2009	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* In Sweden, there is an unknown number of pupils with SEN who are fully included in mainstream classes. Data is not collected relating to these pupils.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	- *	-	
6. Compulsory age phase	The compulsory age phase is 7 to 16 years. Primary age phase is 7 to 9 years. Secondary age phase is 10 to 16 years.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	A majority of Swedish schools are public, run by municipalities, but an increasing number are independent. Independent schools on the compulsory level need to be certified by the National Agency for Education and they are financed by municipality subsidies. The municipality where the student lives pays the school a 'per student, per year grant'. Independent schools are open to everyone and free of charge.						
8. Legal Definition	Please refer to notes above for a clear indication of which pupils the data refers to.						

of SEN	<p>There is no Legal Definition of SEN. In Sweden education follows the principle of 'a school for all' and the focus is on what kind of support the student needs – access to equivalent education for all. This means that pupils in need of special support should not be treated or defined as a group that is any different from other pupils and their rights are not stated separately. The obligation for schools to attend to all pupils' needs is, however, emphasised.</p> <p>Pupils in need of special support have the right to specialist provision. Special support shall be given to pupils who have difficulties in completing their education successfully. If a pupil needs special support an Action Plan shall be drawn up. The regulations regarding plans for pupils in need of special support have been further clarified. The pupil's need is to be assessed and the subsequent Action Plan shall contain information regarding the pupil's needs, what measures will be taken and how these measures will be followed up and evaluated. All education corresponds as far as possible to the National curricular, but with the emphasis upon meeting individual learning needs. In a few circumstances, this provision is offered in special settings, e.g. Special Schools with sign language communication are available for pupils with severe hearing impairments.</p> <p>Reference: All information is taken from Swedish school law and National curriculum documents, e.g. Education Act (1985:1100) Ch.1. General Provisions, Curriculum for the Pre-school Lpfo 98, Curriculum for the Compulsory School System, the Pre-School Class and the Leisure-time Centre Lpo 94, Curriculum for the Non-Compulsory School System Lpf 94.</p>
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SWITZERLAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	734,519		42,875			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	777,394	2008/2009
	445,440	289,079	20,874	22,001		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	29,668		11,977			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	41,645 *	2008/2009
	18,655	11,013	6,774	5,203		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,494		10,729			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	16,223 *	2008/2009
	3,342	2,152	6,130	4,599		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	24,174		1,248			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	25,422 *	2008/2009
	15,313	8,861	644	604		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	- *	-
	-	-	-	-		
6. Compulsory age phase	4–17 years. Primary education is from 4 to 12 years and secondary from 13 to 17 years.					
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public schools are fully funded by the government; the private sector includes schools with or without public subsidies.					

8. Legal Definition of SEN

Inter-cantonal agreement of collaboration in the domain of Special Needs Education:

Individuals entitled to benefits:

Children and youth from birth on to 20 years of age, living in Switzerland, have the right to adequate provision of special educational services, providing that the following conditions are met:

- Prior to compulsory education: if it can be established that the development of the child is limited or at risk or that following instruction in a mainstream classrooms without specific support will not be possible for the child;
- During compulsory education: if it can be established that possibilities of development and education are limited in such a manner that instruction in mainstream classrooms cannot be followed without specific support any more or if other special educational needs are established.

Art 3. Inter-cantonal Agreement of Collaboration in the Domain of Special Needs Education, 25th October 2007.

(Interkantonale Vereinbarung über die Zusammenarbeit im Bereich der Sonderpädagogik vom 25.Oktober 2007).

UNITED KINGDOM – ENGLAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils <i>(including those with SEN)</i>	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Department for Children, Schools and Families (DCSF). SFR 14/2009 – Special Educational Needs (SEN) in England, January 2009 (Table 1a). * For all data, it is not possible to give an exact primary/secondary school split. This applies to questions 1 to 5. It is not possible to say how many pupils are above compulsory school age as published data on pupils with statements does not allow for the removal of either pupils with statements in nursery classes (under the age of 5) within primary phase schools (either mainstream or special), or pupils with statements over the age of 16 in secondary phase schools (either mainstream or special). This is explained in question 6. The data has been rounded up to the nearest 10.
	7,321,650		712,040				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	8,033,690 *	2008/2009	
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN <i>(in all educational settings)</i>	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: DCSF. SFR 14/2009 – SEN in England, January 2009 (Table 2). * All data covers pupils with statements (official recognition of SEN) only. This applies to all data presented in questions 2 to 5.
	213,610		12,310				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	225,920 *	2008/2009	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: DCSF. SFR 14/2009 – SEN in England, January 2009 (Table 2). * This figure is for all pupils in some form of segregated school. The breakdown is: in the public sector maintained special schools (including foundation schools): 83,820; in the private sector non-maintained special schools 3,640; independent special schools: 6,800, and
	83,820		12,310				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	96,130 *	2008/2009	

	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	other independent schools: 1,870.
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	16,190		- **		16,190 *	2008/2009	<p>Source: DCSF. SFR 14/2009 – SEN in England, January 2009 (Table 2).</p> <p>* This figure is for all pupils in some form of segregated class in a mainstream school. The breakdown is: resourced provision/special classes in maintained mainstream schools: 9,040; SEN units in maintained mainstream schools: 7,150.</p> <p>However, it should be noted that it is not possible to say to what degree pupils are segregated or included. This varies from provision to provision.</p> <p>** No data is available.</p>
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	113,600		- **		113,600 *	2008/2009	<p>Source: DCSF SFR 14/2009 – SEN in England, January 2009 (Table 2).</p> <p>Please note that these figures are calculated on a very crude indicator (i.e. enrolment at a mainstream or non-mainstream school). Some pupils on roll in mainstream schools may be in segregated classes while some pupils on the roll of special schools may spend the majority of the week in a mainstream classroom. More accurate data on actual practice is not available at the national level.</p> <p>* This figure is for all pupils in fully inclusive settings. The breakdown is: maintained mainstream schools (including foundation schools): 107,640; pupil referral units: 1,870; hospital schools: 130; academies: 2,480; pupils who are excluded and where other arrangements are made for them: 1,480.</p> <p>NB: There are 2,070 pupils who are either awaiting placement or their parents have made alternative arrangements for them. It is not possible to indicate where they are educated and they are not included in these figures.</p> <p>** No data is available.</p>
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			

6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The compulsory school age range is 5 to 16 years. However, published data on pupils with statements does not allow for the removal of either pupils with statements in nursery classes (under the age of 5) within primary phase schools (either mainstream or special), or pupils with statements over the age of 16 in secondary phase schools (either mainstream or special). Data presented above includes these populations.</p> <p>Primary education begins in the year a child is 5 years old and continues until they are 11. Compulsory secondary education is from 11 to 16 years.</p>
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>'Private education' is that which is provided in institutions, which are largely privately funded, receiving most of their income from tuition fees. There is private provision at all levels of education. Private schools are known as independent schools and they do not receive direct government funding, although some independent schools have charitable status and benefit from tax relief and they may also apply for some public support through, for example, the National Lottery funding scheme.</p> <p>All independent / private schools must meet regulatory requirements (Sections 463-478 of the Education Act 1996), which include reaching satisfactory standards of premises, accommodation, instruction and staffing. They must be registered with the Department for Education and Skills (or national equivalent) and are subject to mainstream inspection from Her Majesty's Inspectors to ensure their fitness to be registered.</p> <p>Included pupils of all ages in schools, excluded pupils in maintained and direct grant nursery schools: while they are not required to follow the national curriculum, independent/private schools must offer a curriculum of sufficient range and depth to be appropriate for the age, aptitude, ability and special educational needs of the pupils placed there.</p> <p>Non-maintained special schools (NMSS) are schools in England approved by the Secretary of State for Education as special schools that are not maintained by the state, but charge fees on a non-profit-making basis. Most non-maintained special schools are run by major charities or charitable trusts. It should be noted that most places in NMSS are purchased by local authorities for pupils for whom there is no available appropriate provision in a maintained school: parents rarely pay fees directly in these schools.</p>
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>It is set out in the Education Act 1996: 312 Meaning of 'special educational needs' and 'special educational provision' etc.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A child has 'special educational needs' for the purposes of this Act if he has a learning difficulty which calls for special educational provision to be made for him. 2) Subject to subsection (3) (and except for the purposes of [section 15A or 15B]) a child has a 'learning difficulty' for the purposes of this Act if (a) he has a significantly greater difficulty in learning than the majority of children of his age, (b) he has a disability which either prevents or hinders him from making use of educational facilities of a kind generally provided for children of his age in schools within the area of the local education authority, or (c) he is under [compulsory school age] and is, or would be if special educational provision were not made for him, likely to fall within paragraph (a) or (b) when of (...) that age. 3) A child is not to be taken as having a learning difficulty solely because the language (or form of the language) in which he is, or will be, taught is different from a language (or form of a language) which has at any time been spoken in his home. 4) In this Act 'special educational provision' means (a) in relation to a child who has attained the age of two, educational provision which is additional to, or otherwise different from, the educational provision made generally for children of his age in schools maintained by the local education authority (other than special schools) and (b) in relation to a child under that age, educational provision of any kind. 5) In this Part 'child' includes any person who has not attained the age of 19 and is a registered pupil at a school; [maintained school' means any community, foundation or voluntary school or any community or foundation special school not established in a hospital.]

UNITED KINGDOM – NORTHERN IRELAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	274,274		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	274,274	2009/2010
	154,887	119,387	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	12,747		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	12,747	2009/2010
	6,140	6,607	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	3,711		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	3,711	2009/2010
	1,645	2,066	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,705		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,705	2009/2010
	915	790	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	7,331		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	7,331	2009/2010
	3,580	3,751	-	-		
6. Compulsory age phase	4 years of age to 16 years of age as defined in Article 46 of the Education and Libraries (Northern Ireland) (Order 1986).					

7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Census data does not include information on independent / private sector schools. Such schools operate outside the SEN Framework.
8. Legal Definition of SEN	Article 3 of the Education (Northern Ireland) Order 1996 defines a child as having special educational needs if he or she has a learning difficulty that calls for special educational provision to be made for him or her.

UNITED KINGDOM – SCOTLAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	617,416		30,507 *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	647,923	2009/2010
	369,980	247,436	11,527	18,980		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	41,158		4,199			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	45,357 *	2009/2010
	22,763	18,395	1,187	3,012		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,677		982			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	6,659 *	2009/2010
	2,887	2,790	88	894		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,481		0			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,481 *	2009/2010
	948	533	0	0		
<p>Source: The Scottish Government, Pupils in Scotland 2009 Statistical Bulletin and Independent School Census. This covers all pupils. * All data for pupils in private education includes pupils outside the compulsory school age range. This applies to questions 1–5.</p> <p>Source: The Scottish Government. * In Scotland the concept of Additional Support Needs (ASN) is used. Please see question 8 below for a full definition.</p> <p>Source: The Scottish Government. * All pupils based in special schools are included here regardless of the time they spend in mainstream classes.</p> <p>Source: The Scottish Government. * Includes pupils with ASN in mainstream schools who spend 20% or less of their time in mainstream classes. Due to small numbers of pupils in segregated classes in private sector, these pupils have been included in the fully inclusive setting figures to prevent disclosure. (Disclosure relates to identification of individuals in cases where small numbers are involved. Scotland does not normally publish small numbers to avoid the risk of having them being identified. In this particular case, instead of removing them altogether the small figure is included within inclusive settings statistics.)</p>						

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: The Scottish Government. Includes all pupils with ASN in mainstream schools who spend less than 20% of their time in segregated special classes.
	34,000		3,217				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	18,928	15,072	1,099	2,118			
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The usual arrangements for pupils entering the first class of primary school are that children whose 5th birthday falls between the start of March and the end of February start school together in the August in the middle of that period. However, parents may choose to defer entry.</p> <p>Pupils who reach the age of 16 between 1 March and 30 September of a given year can leave that summer, or if they reach 16 from 1 October to the following end of February can leave at the end of winter term during that period.</p> <p>Public sector: primary phase pupils are pupils aged 4 or older in primary schools or pupils aged 4 to 11 years in special schools. Secondary phase pupils are pupils in secondary schools aged under 16 or pupils aged 12 to 15 years in special schools. Ages are as at 30th September 2009.</p> <p>Private sector: primary phase pupils above are in primary schools or are pupils under 12 in special schools. Secondary phase pupils are pupils in secondary schools or pupils aged 12 or over in special schools. Ages at 31st December 2009.</p>						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Publicly funded schools are local authority and grant-aided schools. A grant-aided school is a school in receipt of funding from the Scottish Government.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Definition of Additional Support Needs (ASN) in The Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2004:</p> <p>(1) A child or young person has additional support needs for the purposes of this Act where, for whatever reason, the child or young person is, or is likely to be, unable without the provision of additional support to benefit from school education provided or to be provided for the child or young person.</p> <p>(2) In subsection (1), the reference to school education includes, in particular, such education directed to the development of the personality, talents and mental and physical abilities of the child or young person to their fullest potential.</p> <p>(3) In this Act, 'additional support' means:</p> <p>(a) in relation to a prescribed pre-school child, a child of school age or a young person receiving school education, provision which is additional to, or otherwise different from, the additional provision made generally for children or, as the case may be, young persons of the same age in schools (other than special schools) under the management of the education authority for the area to which the child or young person belongs;</p> <p>(b) in relation to a child under school other than a prescribed pre-school child, such educational provision as is appropriate in the circumstances.</p>						

UNITED KINGDOM – WALES

Question	Data				Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	370,643		6,860 *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	377,503	2008/2009
	194,329	176,314	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	12,418		477 *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	12,895	2008/2009
	-	-	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	3,070		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	3,070 *	2008/2009
	-	-	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,843		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,843 *	2008/2009
	-	-	-	-		

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Schools in Wales General Statistics 2009. * Data is not available regarding the split into primary and secondary age phases in fully inclusive settings.
	6,982		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-			
					6,982 *	2008/2009	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory school age is classed as pupils aged 5–15 years of age. Data collection is completed for the following 3 categories: Under 5, 5–15 and 16 and over. It is not split into primary and secondary in most cases.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public sector education – education which is controlled by the Government. Private sector education – education which is not controlled but the Government or Local Education Authorities and run privately.						
8. Legal Definition of SEN	<p>Children have special educational needs if they have a learning difficulty which calls for special educational provision to be made for them.</p> <p>Children have a learning difficulty if they:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Have a significantly greater difficulty in learning than the majority of children of the same age; or b) Have a disability which prevents or hinders them from making use of educational facility of a kind generally provided for children of the same age in schools within the area of the local education authority; c) Are under compulsory school age and fall within the definition at (a) or (b) above or would do so if special educational provision was not made for them. <p>Special educational provision means:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) For children of two or over, educational provision which is additional to, or otherwise different from, the educational provision made generally available for children of their age in schools maintained by the LEA, other than special schools, in the area; b) For children under two, educational provision of any kind. <p>SEN Code of Practice for Wales 2002.</p>						

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